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Criteria for Teachers' Professional Competence in Design of Inclusive Education

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Abstract

Education of children with disabilities in educational institutions instead of schools for exceptional children or remedial classes is a new and promising approach to the educational process in Russian pedagogy. The study allows us to conclude as follows: 1. The readiness of future teachers to work in the context of inclusive education should be a conscious and stable personality characteristic, which is a significant criterion in teaching the children with disabilities and is determined by the focus on the implementation of the principles of inclusion in professional activities. 2. The structure of inclusive readiness consists of inclusive culture; inclusive theory; the formation of civic identity of the future special education teacher; inclusive practice. 3. The main criteria for future teachers' readiness to work in the context of inclusive education are as follows: value-motivational (adoption of the values of inclusion and their implementation in the pedagogical inclusive educational environment); personal (personal qualities of the teacher providing better organization of the pedagogical inclusive process); cognitive (awareness of the fundamentals of inclusive education); activity (activity of immersiveness in solving the problems of inclusive education) [3]. Based on the foregoing, the aim of the study is to improve the quality of training of future teachers for work in the context of inclusive education through the development of criteria for professional readiness. Research methods: theoretical (the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, comparison of existing patterns of inclusive training of teachers), empirical (involved observation, expert assessment), interrogatory, experimental (summative, formative and control experiments) methods of psychological and pedagogical research. The experimental test was carried out at the Faculty of Primary Education of the Dagestan State Pedagogical University. The study involved 51 students. The effectiveness of training students of pedagogical universities for work in a heterogeneous educational environment can be increased if: 1. Inclusive readiness is considered as one of the key components of professional training of future teachers. 2. The essence of the definition of "teacher's professional inclusive readiness" is specified. 3. Inclusive culture is considered as the foundation for the formation of inclusive readiness.

Keywords: inclusive education, inclusion, defectology, children with disabilities, professional readiness, educational environment.

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Introduction

The urgency of the problem. We need to understand that trends in the development of both special (correctional) and inclusive education become reality and require the solution of many problems: primarily, training specialists, creating an accessible environment, developing adaptive educational programs, individual educational routes for children with various special needs, as well as the necessity for retraining and training of teachers, on the basis of advanced special faculties and departments, innovative special (remedial) schools, rehabilitation centers (Bazhukova, 2016).

To date, the urgent need for the modern educational system is the transition of special (correctional) institutions to adaptive educational programs, and to adaptive principal educational programs for children with disabilities. The content of the programs is based on the State Educational Standards, but their implementation requires significant changes in the methods in the context of new understanding of the goals of the modern special (correctional) and inclusive school, since adaptive educational programs are focused on inclusion at various levels of education, and on training pupils with vision and hearing impairments, musculoskeletal disorders, mental retardation, mild mental deficiency, autistic spectrum disorders for social, domestic and labor orientation and integration into the general society.

A necessary stage is the transition to adaptive educational programs, which are developed taking into account the recommendations of the psychological, medical and pedagogical commission (PMPC), the individual rehabilitation program for the disabled person, including activity area, analysis and selection of content; changes in the structure and timeframe; the use of a variety of innovative forms, methods and techniques of organizing teaching, educational, correctional and rehabilitation activities.

The analysis is carried out due to the requirements of the State Educational Standards, the content of exemplary programs, including those for children with disabilities. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities and specifics of the psychophysical development of children with disabilities (according to the documents presented by parents and the recommendations of the PMPC). The design of adaptive educational program (AEP) takes into account its structural components of the FSES, as well as

special educational needs of children with disabilities and determines individual boundaries and timeframe of their learning.

It is necessary to draw the attention of AEP developers to a clear articulation of the goals of AEPs, the definition of the range of tasks that specify the objectives of the adaptive educational program. The specificity of children with disabilities requires accounting the peculiarities of their development to create adequate conditions for their rehabilitation and socialization in the modern society.

Adaptive educational programs should consider the specificity and personal characteristics of each child with disabilities, rely on the principles of defectologic education; compensatory training and education; consideration of individual differences; social adaptation and rehabilitation, building an individual educational route; psychological, medical and pedagogical support, special adequate assistance accounting the psychophysical health of children with disabilities, on the principles of humanism, value-oriented education and training; the principle of systematic unity of diagnostics, correction, compensation, development; the principle of complex interaction of managers, doctors, teachers, psychologists, parents and their children (Mallaev, Omarova, & Bazhukova, 2019).

The implementation of the adaptive program requires creation of special conditions to achieve the main objective, and it will allow pupils to receive a high-quality adequate education and provide the graduates' active socialization and adaptation in the surrounding society, and readiness to join in the integrated cultural and educational system of the new school (Mallaev, 2017).

The transition to adaptive and principal educational programs involves planning and participation of a wide range of specialists, such as educators, teachers, psychologists, special education teachers, etc., in their implementation.

Adaptive educational programs in inclusion are transitional for the implementation of principal educational programs. The success of correctional work, teaching and education of children with disabilities according to the AEPs is provided by subject teachers and a group of specialists with defectologic education, while psychological and pedagogical support is provided by tutors, social teachers, and doctors (Bazhukova, 2017).

This arrangement is provided by the educational pedagogical community of mass and special (defectologic) education, scientific and methodological support of inclusive education should be carried out by scientists, specialists from the departments of corrective pedagogy, special psychology, defectology of

the corresponding departments of universities, and the directors of departments of education and their specialists should ensure the arrangement of an accessible environment and the work of PMPC.

Such an approach will create conditions for the development and implementation of the tasks of correctional and inclusive education, including preparing and implementing AEPs with the involvement of the above specialists, experts, teachers, tutors, parents and specialists of the specific type of special (correctional) school. This is one of the significant conditions for the transition to adaptive educational programs that ensure the effectiveness of the transition and step by step learning of the content of these programs, taking into account the features of the development of each child with disabilities.

Discussion

The first steps in the transition of children with disabilities to the inclusive education system revealed an inadequate reaction of the society, specialists, parents, and there was a wrong opinion concerning the reduction of the system of special (correctional) education. The system of inclusive education that has developed in the Western world for many decades shows that the basic condition for effective inclusion is interaction with leading schools (Matasov, 2008). For example, the experience gained for many years at the Republican Rehabilitation Center for children with disabilities, led by the People's Teacher of the USSR Murtuzalieva, experimentally proved its innovativeness and relevance for the whole Russia.

Adoption of the new Federal State Educational Standards and their content do not meet the requirements of training teachers and psychologists for inclusive education. Statutory and regulatory acts present the ways of solving problems in the systems of special and inclusive education for people with disabilities, without taking into account the lack of work experience, vocational training, retraining and advanced training of special education teachers. For example, a teacher of primary school lacks the competencies of inclusive education and faces the problems in the implementation of educational process with children with disabilities (Bazhukova, 2017).

Modern realities and prospects for the development of the system of defectologic education provide new changes in various directions within the framework of the new "Law on Education". In accordance with Part 1 of Article 79 of Federal Law dated December 29, 2012, No.273 "On Education in the Russian Federation" (hereinafter referred to as the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation"), "... the content of education and the conditions for training and education of children with disabilities are determined by the adaptive educational program, and for the disabled in accordance with the individual rehabilitation program as well" (Bazhukova, 2016).

Literature review

It is based on statutory and regulatory framework: adoption of the National Doctrine of the Russian Federation (2000), which sets the goals for teaching and education of younger generations up to 2025, accession of Russia to the Bologna Declaration (2003), and adoption of the Federal Law “On Education in the Russian Federation” (2012). In 2011, the State Program “Accessible Environment” was launched, and its purpose was to increase the adaptability of Russian towns and cities for people with disabilities. This required the implementation of projects on creation of accessible environment for people with disabilities, allowing them to integrate into the society. It is important to note that the problem of inclusive characteristics in the education system has been studied by Russian and foreign researchers (Mallaev, 2017; Malofeev, 1996; Levchenko, 2003; Neretina, 2010; Omarova, 1999; Staroverova, 2011). Many articles deal with generic issues of professional competence of teachers, as well as the peculiarities of training teachers for work in the context of the integration of children with disabilities into the general education environment (Vodennikova, 2013; Kuzmina, 1990; Slastenin, 1976; Shumilovskaya, 2011; Khitryuk, 2015). Based on the foregoing, the aim of the study is to improve the quality of training of future teachers for work in the context of inclusive education through the development of criteria for professional readiness.

Methodology

When solving the problem under study, it is essential that the methodological bases that have been correctly developed are of decisive importance. The main of them are well-known methods: retrospectively-logical analysis, diagnosis of the child’s mental state, conversation with parents to identify and establish an accurate diagnosis, study of the anamnesis and the real state of manifestation of neurotic reactions of the child in the retardation of mental development and mild degree of mental retardation in the children with disabilities we surveyed.

The goal of our study is to improve the quality of training of future teachers for work in the context of inclusive education through the development of criteria of professional readiness. The main methods of our research are theoretical (the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, comparison of existing patterns of inclusive training of teachers), empirical (involved observation, expert assessment), interrogatory, experimental (summative, formative and control experiments) methods of psychological and pedagogical research. The experimental test was carried out at the Faculty of Primary Education of the Dagestan State Pedagogical University. The study involved 51 students.

Results

Our study and experience in working with children with disabilities and specifically with children with developmental delay and mild degree of mental retardation with reliance on experience of foreign and domestic researchers allowed us to establish the following: 1. The readiness of future teachers to work in the context of inclusive education should be a conscious and stable personality characteristic, which is a significant criterion in teaching the children with disabilities and is determined by the focus on the implementation of the principles of inclusion in professional activities. 2. The structure of inclusive readiness consists of inclusive culture; inclusive theory; the formation of civic identity of the future special education teacher; inclusive practice. 3. The main criteria for future teachers' readiness to work in the context of inclusive education are as follows (Voznyak, 2015): value-motivational (adoption of the values of inclusion and their implementation in the pedagogical inclusive educational environment); personal (personal qualities of the teacher providing better organization of the pedagogical inclusive process); cognitive (awareness of the fundamentals of inclusive education); activity (activity of immersiveness in solving the problems of inclusive education).

The results of the study can be used in the development of working programs of practices implemented within the framework of inclusive education, in the implementation of comparative studies to develop the methodology for practical training of teachers.

Conclusion

This arrangement is provided by the educational pedagogical community of mass and special (defectologic) education, scientific and methodological support of inclusive education should be carried out by scientists, specialists from the departments of corrective pedagogy, special psychology, defectology of the corresponding departments of universities, and the directors of departments of education and their specialists should ensure the arrangement of an accessible environment and the work of PMPC.

Such an approach will create conditions for the development and implementation of the tasks of correctional and inclusive education, including preparing and implementing AEPs with the involvement of the above specialists, experts, teachers, tutors, parents and specialists of the specific type of special (correctional) school. This is one of the significant conditions for the transition to adaptive educational programs that ensure the effectiveness of the transition and step by step learning of the content of these programs, taking into account the features of the development of each child with disabilities.

Thus, summing up the conducted research, it should be noted that the effectiveness of training students of pedagogical universities for work in a heterogeneous educational environment can be increased if: 1. Inclusive readiness is considered as one of the key components of professional training of future teachers (Mallaev, Omarova, & Bazhukova, 2019). 2. The essence of the definition of “teacher’s professional inclusive readiness” is specified. 3. Inclusive culture is considered as the foundation for the formation of inclusive readiness. 4. A compulsory educational subject for training future teachers for work in the system of inclusive education is included in the Federal State Educational Standards of new generations of Higher Pedagogical Education.

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